

Boron Complexes of Monofunctional Bidentate and Bifunctional Tridentate Schiff Bases

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Boron Schiff base complexes of the type $(\text{AcO})_2\text{B}(\text{SB})$ and $(\text{AcO})_2\text{B}(\text{SBH})$ [where SB^- and SBH^- represent the anions of monofunctional bidentate and bifunctional tridentate Schiff bases having the donor systems $\text{N}-\text{OH}$ and $\text{HO}-\text{N}-\text{OH}$ respectively] have been synthesized by the interaction of boric acid with the Schiff bases in acetic anhydride medium. Schiff bases having a functional OH group ortho to the azomethine ($>\text{C}=\text{N}$) group such as $o\text{-HOC}_6\text{H}_4\text{C}(\text{CH}_3):\text{NR}$ [where $\text{R}=-n\text{-C}_6\text{H}_7$, $-iso\text{-C}_6\text{H}_7$, $-n\text{-C}_4\text{H}_9$, $-sec\text{-C}_4\text{H}_9$, $-t\text{-C}_4\text{H}_9$, and $-\text{C}_6\text{H}_5$] and $o\text{-HOC}_6\text{H}_4\text{C}(\text{CH}_3):\text{NXOH}$ [where $\text{X}=-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2-$, $-\text{CH}_2\text{CHCH}_2$ and $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{C}(\text{HCH}_2)-$] have been found to react with boric acid only equimolarly regardless of the stoichiometry of the reactants. All the complexes have been synthesized almost in quantitative yields and characterized by their molar conductance and molecular weight determination in dimethyl-formamide and boiling chloroform respectively. Their infrared spectra have also been recorded.

ALTHOUGH literature records the synthesis of a few Schiff base complexes¹⁻⁵ of boron no systematic attempt seems to have been made so far to study such type of compounds. In earlier communications⁶⁻⁸, a variety of boron complexes of Schiff bases have been reported and the results achieved thereof were quite encouraging. It was, therefore, considered of interest to prepare such types of derivatives during the course of the present investigations.

The present paper describes the reaction of boric acid with monofunctional bidentate and bifunctional tridentate Schiff bases derived by the condensation of *o*-hydroxyacetophenone with alkylamines, aniline or hydroxyalkylamines.

Experimental

Dimethylformamide (E. Merck) was dehydrated by keeping over anhydrous sodium carbonate for one day, decanted and then distilled. It was further redistilled under reduced pressure (55°/35 mm). Chloroform (B.D.H.) was dried by storage over fused calcium chloride for two days and then decanted off. It was redistilled twice after refluxing over aluminium isopropoxide (b.p.61°). Acetic anhydride (B. D. H.) was distilled before use whereas boric acid (B.D.H. AR) was used without further purification.

Preparation of the Schiff bases : Schiff bases were prepared by mixing *o*-hydroxyacetophenone with alkylamines, aniline or hydroxyalkylamines equimolarly in benzene. An exothermic reaction took place resulting in a clear yellow coloured solution. The contents were refluxed over a fractionating column followed by continuous removal of water-benzene azeotrope till the distillate attained a constant temperature of 80°. Excess of the solvent was removed and the products were distilled under

reduced pressure. Their analysis and physical properties are enlisted in Tables 1 and 2.

Preparation of boron Schiff base derivatives : Boric acid was dissolved in acetic anhydride by refluxing it gently. The solution was cooled to room temperature and calculated amount of the Schiff base was added. The resulting yellow solution was allowed to stand overnight whereby its colour changed to blue or dark green. Excess of the solvent was removed over pump and finally the products were vacuum dried. The details of their synthesis, analysis and physical properties are recorded in Tables 3 and 4.

Analytical methods and physical measurements : For the estimation of boron and acetoxy group in the boron Schiff base derivatives a weighed amount of the sample was hydrolyzed with water. The acetic acid produced was titrated against standard sodium hydroxide solution using phenolphthalein as indicator. Mannitol was added after the end point was reached and the titration continued to the end point. The first titre value determines the acetoxy content of the compound, whereas the titre value recorded after the addition of mannitol corresponds to its boron content⁹.

Nitrogen was estimated by the Kjeldahl method. Results of carbon and hydrogen analysis were supplied by the Department of Pure Chemistry, University College of Science, Calcutta.

Molecular weights were determined in chloroform with the help of a semi-micro ebulliometer (Gallen Kamp) using thermistor sensing. The molar conductance measurements were made at $28 \pm 1^\circ$ by a conductivity bridge type 235 (Anu Vidyut, Roorkee) with the cell having a cell constant of 0.78 cm^{-1} . Infrared spectra were recorded in the range $4000\text{-}625 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ on a Unicam SP-1025 spectrophotometer using KBr optics.

TABLE 1—MONOFUNCTIONAL BIDENTATE SCHIFF BASES AND THEIR ANALYSES

Sl. No.	Schiff base	Physical Characteristics			Analysis(%)		
		Colour and State	b.p. (°C/mm)	m.p. (°C)	Carbon Found (Calcd.)	Hydrogen Found (Calcd.)	Nitrogen Found (Calcd.)
1.	<i>o</i> -Hydroxyacetophenone- <i>n</i> -propylimine (C ₁₁ H ₁₅ NO)	Yellow solid	140/4.0	45-46	74.48 (74.57)	8.42 (8.47)	7.93 (7.91)
2.	<i>o</i> -Hydroxyacetophenone- <i>isopropylimine</i> (C ₁₁ H ₁₅ NO)*	Yellow liquid	123/2.8	—	74.43 (74.57)	8.44 (8.47)	7.90 (7.91)
3.	<i>o</i> -Hydroxyacetophenone- <i>n</i> -butylimine (C ₁₂ H ₁₇ NO)	Yellow solid	98/0.1-0.2	65-66	75.26 (75.39)	8.90 (8.96)	7.45 (7.32)
4.	<i>o</i> -Hydroxyacetophenone- <i>sec</i> -butylimine (C ₁₂ H ₁₇ NO)**	Yellow liquid	131/2.3	—	75.25 (75.39)	8.88 (8.96)	7.35 (7.32)
5.	<i>o</i> -Hydroxyacetophenone- <i>t</i> -butylimine (C ₁₂ H ₁₇ NO)***	Yellow solid	92/1.2	—	75.32 (75.39)	8.87 (8.96)	7.29 (7.32)
6.	<i>o</i> -Hydroxyacetophenoneanil (C ₁₄ H ₁₉ NO)	Yellow solid	135/0.2-0.3	79.80	79.48 (79.60)	6.16 (6.21)	6.59 (6.63)

*, ** and *** have been used to distinguish between the compounds of same molecular formula.

TABLE 2—SCHIFF BASES AND THEIR ANALYSIS

Sl. No.	Schiff base	Physical Characteristics			Analysis(%)		
		State	m.p. (°C)	b.p. (°C/mm)	C Found (Calcd.)	H Found (Calcd.)	N Found (Calcd.)
1.	<i>o</i> -Hydroxyacetophenone-2-hydroxyethylimine (C ₁₀ H ₁₃ NO ₂)	Yellow solid	96	149-150/0.1	66.97 (67.01)	7.56 (7.31)	7.72 (7.81)
2.	<i>o</i> -Hydroxyacetophenone-2-hydroxy-1-propylimine (C ₁₁ H ₁₅ NO ₂)	Yellow solid	91	164-165/1.2	68.12 (69.37)	7.67 (7.82)	7.34 (7.25)
3.	<i>o</i> -Hydroxyacetophenone-1-hydroxy-2-butylimine (C ₁₂ H ₁₇ NO ₂)	Highly viscous yellow solid	—	137-138/0.3	69.27 (69.55)	8.19 (8.27)	6.71 (6.76)

TABLE 3—REACTIONS OF BORIC ACID WITH MONOFUNCTIONAL BIDENTATE SCHIFF BASES

H ₃ BO ₃ (g)	Schiff base (g)	Product and Characteristics	m.p. (°C)	Analysis (%)			Molecular weight Found (Calcd.)
				B Found (Calcd.)	N Found (Calcd.)	OAc Found (Calcd.)	
0.63	C ₁₁ H ₁₅ NO 1.81	B(OAc) ₂ (C ₁₁ H ₁₅ NO) Bluish grey solid, soluble in chloroform.	133	3.50 (3.54)	4.52 (4.59)	39.32 (38.70)	296 (305)
0.91	C ₁₁ H ₁₅ NO* 2.61	B(OAc) ₂ (C ₁₁ H ₁₅ NO)* Light yellow solid, soluble in chloroform.	141	3.49 (3.54)	4.54 (4.59)	38.08 (38.70)	293 (305)
0.78	C ₁₂ H ₁₇ NO 2.42	B(OAc) ₂ (C ₁₂ H ₁₇ NO) Light yellow solid, soluble in chloroform.	128	3.36 (3.39)	4.30 (4.39)	36.98 (37.23)	311 (319)
0.76	C ₁₂ H ₁₇ NO** 2.35	B(OAc) ₂ (C ₁₂ H ₁₇ NO)** Light yellow solid, soluble in chloroform.	61	3.38 (3.39)	4.29 (4.39)	36.53 (37.23)	308 (319)
0.80	C ₁₂ H ₁₇ NO*** 2.49	B(OAc) ₂ (C ₁₂ H ₁₇ NO)*** Light yellow solid, soluble in chloroform.	115	3.35 (3.39)	4.33 (4.39)	37.08 (37.23)	310 (319)
0.90	C ₁₄ H ₁₉ NO 3.07	B(OAc) ₂ (C ₁₄ H ₁₉ NO) Violet solid, soluble in chloroform.	185	3.15 (3.19)	4.09 (4.13)	33.64 (34.81)	326 (339)

TABLE 4—REACTIONS OF BORIC ACID WITH BIFUNCTIONAL TRIDENTATE SCHIFF BASES

H ₃ BO ₃ (g)	Schiff base (g)	Product and Characteristics	m.p. °C	Analysis %			Molecular weight Found (Calcd.)
				B Found (Calcd.)	N Found (Calcd.)	OAc Found (Calcd.)	
0.64	C ₁₀ H ₁₃ NO ₂ 1.86	B(OAc) ₃ (C ₁₀ H ₁₃ NO ₂) Green solid, soluble in chloroform.	79	3.47 (3.52)	4.59 (4.56)	37.54 (38.47)	295 (307)
0.59	C ₁₁ H ₁₅ NO ₂ 1.84	B(OAc) ₃ (C ₁₁ H ₁₅ NO ₂) Green solid, soluble in chloroform.	91	3.34 (3.37)	4.26 (4.36)	35.69 (36.77)	306 (321)
0.94	C ₁₂ H ₁₇ NO ₂ 3.16	B(OAc) ₃ (C ₁₂ H ₁₇ NO ₂) Dark green solid, soluble in chloroform.	106	3.20 (3.23)	4.25 (4.28)	34.48 (35.24)	328 (335)

Results and Discussion

The equimolar reactions of boric acid with the Schiff bases in acetic anhydride medium may be depicted in the following two steps :

(where SBH and SBH₂ represent monofunctional bidentate and bifunctional tridentate Schiff base molecules respectively).

Similar reactions were carried out in higher molar ratios but even after prolonged refluxing only 1 : 1 derivatives could be isolated. The bifunctional tridentate Schiff bases behave in these reactions as monofunctional bidentate ligands and the reacting group is probably the phenolic one. The presence of one of the functional groups as unreacted in these derivatives is probably due to the stable tetracoordinated state of boron.

The resulting derivatives are coloured and non-distillable solids. They are stable to the dry atmosphere but undergo rapid hydrolysis liberating acetic acid. The exchange reaction of these derivatives with 2-methylpentane-2, 4-diol was found to be quite slow and could not be completed even after 70-80 hrs of refluxing. This probably indicates a stable tetracoordinated state for the central boron atom in these compounds.

All these derivatives are soluble in chloroform and the ebullioscopic determinations of molecular weights in boiling chloroform show them to be monomers. Thus, these derivatives may be represented by the following tentative structures (I) and (II) :

(I)

(II)

Infrared spectra : A comparison of the infrared spectra of the Schiff bases with their boron complexes has revealed the following important features :

(i) The broad and weak absorption bands observed in the regions 3100-3000 and 3300-3100 cm⁻¹ in the spectra of the monofunctional bidentate and the bifunctional tridentate Schiff bases respectively may be assigned to the intramolecularly (O-H...N) and intermolecularly (O-H...O) hydrogen bonded νOH. The disappearance of the above band in the spectra of boron complexes of monofunctional bidentate ligands indicates coordination of boron to the

phenolic oxygen. On the other hand, the band observed in the region 3300-3100 cm⁻¹ in the spectra of the boron derivatives of bifunctional tridentate Schiff bases probably indicates that one of the functional OH groups of the ligand remains unreacted.

(ii) A sharp and strong band is observed in the region 1625-1600 cm⁻¹ in the spectra of the ligands and this is due to νC=N. The same band, however, shifts to the higher frequency in the spectra of the corresponding derivatives. The shifting of this band to the higher frequency is probably due to an increase in the bond order of C=N^s caused by the donation of lone pair of electrons by the nitrogen of the ligand to the central boron atom.

(iii) In the spectra of boron Schiff base derivatives two absorption peaks observed at ~1700 and 1355 cm⁻¹ may be attributed to νC=O and νB=O asym. respectively. The same bands have been reported at 1700±10 and 1375±10 cm⁻¹ in the spectra of some boron complexes by earlier workers¹⁰⁻¹². The shifting of the latter band to a lower frequency in the case of the present derivatives is probably due to a decrease in the double bond character of B-O bond on coordination of nitrogen to the boron atom through a dative bond¹³.

Conductance measurements : The molar conductance values for these derivatives range over 10-15 ohm⁻¹cm²mole⁻¹ and thereby indicating their non-electrolytic nature.

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